

ICCM24

24TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS

aimen

TECHNOLOGY CENTRE

Innovation & Technology

Sequential resistance welding of a thermoplastic composite leading edge demonstrator: From laboratory testing to full-scale welding

M. Russello, E. Chemello, R. González Gil, A. Martínez Domínguez, E. Rodríguez Senín

Massimiliano Russello

Team Leader of Composite Welding Technologies

HERWINGT

Ultrasonic Welding

Resistance Welding

Induction Welding

Conduction Welding

Process Understanding

Equipment manufacturing

Automation and Monitoring

Resistance Welding The frame couplings

Scale-up challenge:

- Multiple in-series welds
- Automatic process
- Uniform performance

Sequential Resistance Welding Thermoplastic Leading Edge

Scale-up challenge:

- 2.5 m structure
- Variable thickness
- Uniform performance
- Controllable temperatures
- High key performance

BASE MATERIAL :
High Temperature Thermoplastic
Composites

Current aeronautic needs:

- Innovative materials: Thermoplastics among these
- Flexible and adaptable manufacturing systems
- Shorter manufacturing cycles
- Environmental friendliness
- Energy efficiency
- Higher productivity

THERMOPLASTIC WELDING

- ✓ ROBUST
- ✓ RELIABLE
- ✓ EFFICIENT
- ✓ COMPATIBLE
- ✓ SAFE

Parameters and variables:

- ❖ Pressure
- ❖ Power/Current
- ❖ Time
- ❖ Cooling
- ❖ Part layup and size
- ❖ Conductivity
- ❖ Thickness

Scale-up challenge

Progressive
Scale-up

Welding: Setups
and Parameters
investigation

Analysis, Testing
and data
interpretation:
Performance,
robustness,
processability.

Monitoring:
Process investigation
involving technological
and process parameters,
in-use monitoring

Metal Heating Element

Carbon Based Heating Element

$$\rho_s(m\Omega) = \frac{R(\Omega) \cdot w(mm)}{l(mm)} \cdot 1000$$

The Heating Element – Electrical Properties

The effect of the Heating element Width

MONITORING ADVANTAGES

- ✓ Correlate the technological parameters to the physical changes

UD Type

Fabric Type

Electrical Signal

Tuned Thermal Output

Issues

- Heating element Reliability and Consistency (Electrical and Thermal Properties)
- Component to be welded (Material, Length, Thickness)
- Control and Monitoring

Possible Solutions

- Definition of acceptable processing windows
- Development of a Calibration processes
- Development of a Control and Monitoring System

Thermal Output

- Constant Electrical Input >> Time-Variable Thermal Output
- Variable Electrical Input >> Tuned Thermal Output
 - Batch Calibration >> **Affected by Variability and Setup Variations**
 - Individual Calibration >> **No affected by Variability** but **affected by setup variation**
 - Individual Calibration on Specific Setup >> **No affected by Variability nor by Setup Variations**
 - Real-Time control by Feedback > **No affected by Variability nor by Setup Variations (Complex)**

Batch Calibration

Individual Calibration

Individual Calibration on Setup

Real-Time Monitoring and Control

Real-Time Monitoring and Control

$$T = T_0 + \frac{\rho - \rho_0}{\omega}$$

Laboratory scale....

Demonstrator scale....

**Energy director
installation**

**Tooling and Head
design**

**Automation and
control systems**

**Final Welding
Process**

Other Success Stories

REMARKS

- Future applications of current manufacturing, assembly, and welding technologies are being developed in the direction of rapid, reliable and efficient processes.
- In the aviation industry, as well as other industries, research and analysis on the scalability of manufacturing methods can have a significant impact on future applications.

Headquarters

Laser Applications Centre

Polígono Industrial de Cataboi
SUR-PPI-2 (Sector 2) Parcela 3
E36418 O PORRIÑO
Pontevedra - Spain
Phone: +34 986 344 000

Torneiros Facilities

Armando Priegue Building

Relva 27 A – Torneiros
E36410 O PORRIÑO
Pontevedra – Spain
Phone: +34 986 344 000

A Coruña Office

Polígono Industrial de Pocomaco
Parcela D-22 Oficina 20
E15190 A Coruña - Spain
Phone.: +34 637 127 253

Madrid Office

C/ Rodríguez San Pedro, 2
Planta 6, Oficina 609 Edificio Inter
E28015 Madrid - Spain
Phone: +34 687 448 915

North Office

Parque Tecnológico de Zamudio
Edificio 103, Planta 2
E48170 ZAMUDIO - Vizcaya
Phone: +34 662 489 181

aimen@aimen.es
www.aimen.es

